

Access to Healthcare in Rural Areas: a Hospital-level Analysis*

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Providing high-quality healthcare in rural and low-density areas is increasingly challenging due to aging, workforce shortages, and geographic isolation. This paper examines hospital performance in rural areas in Italy using hospital-level data from the National Clinical Outcomes Programme for the years 2015–2022. We analyze four key indicators capturing procedural efficiency, appropriateness of care, emergency responsiveness, and longer-term outcomes: timely surgery for femur fractures, primary caesarean section rates, 30-day mortality after acute myocardial infarction, and 1-year mortality after stroke. Combining these outcomes with detailed geographic, socio-economic and demographic information at the hospital catchment-area level, we assess whether hospitals serving predominantly rural populations perform differently from those serving more urban areas. The results show that rural localities are associated with significantly worse outcomes for three of the four indicators, even after controlling for healthcare supply, income, and regional fixed effects. These findings highlight persistent spatial inequalities in healthcare quality and the need for place-based policy interventions targeting rural areas.

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1. Introduction

Healthcare systems around the world are facing a number of common challenges. Demographic change is causing both increasing demand for healthcare services and shortages of healthcare workers. Both of these issues are likely to affect disproportionately less attractive geographical areas or professions. Technological changes push towards centralization of acute hospital services, typically benefiting higher-density areas. The increased share of elderly patients with multiple co-morbidities increases not only the demand on hospital services, but also the need for efficient and diffused territorial services for post-acute care. Around the world urban population is also increasing, leaving vast rural areas less and less densely populated, with a disproportionately elderly population. All of these factors, related to both supply and demand of healthcare services, make provision in rural areas more challenging.

Italy is a very good example of these dynamics: the share of doctors over 55 years old is the highest in Western Europe (OECD, 2025), population at large is aging and Southern and rural Italy are experiencing even stronger contractions of births and emigration rates.

This paper contributes to the literature on the challenges of providing healthcare in rural areas, and more broadly to the literature on the socio-economic, geographic and environmental determinants of healthcare outcomes. We innovate on most of the existing contributions as we do not rely on region or country level health measures, but on a novel dataset of hospital-level indices encompassing different dimensions of healthcare provisions, together with a battery of geographic, social and economic controls from public sources. We leverage on the Clinical Outcome Program (*Programma Nazionale Esiti*, PNE), which records and publishes yearly up to 200 process, mortality and morbidity indicators together with statistics on the number of procedures for the universe of public and private-accredited hospitals. We concentrate on four measures, representing the array of services a healthcare system provides: share of patients operated within two days for femur fracture (catching procedural efficiency in a routine operation), the share of primary C-section (catching both the hospital quality in delivering appropriate treatments, together with the efficiency of emergency and territorial network in sparsely populated areas), 30-day mortality for acute myocardial infarction (catching the effect of an efficient emergency network and cardiological care) and finally 1-year mortality for stroke (highlighting also the importance of follow-up treatments both at the hospital and territorial level).

The aim of this study is to separate factors generically related to the supply and demand of healthcare services (number of doctors, number of elderly people, income) with those more directly related to the challenges of remote areas.

Our paper broadly relates to the literature on the socio-economic and geographic determi-

nants of healthcare outcomes. Most of this literature leverages on regional level outcomes and vital statistics record or on linking self-reported health by survey respondents with their geographical location. More rarely individual-level data are used, for either health status or socio-economic condition. Marmot and Wilkinson (2005)'s review analyzes a vast array of research papers to describe the paths through which socio-economic status (SES), personal or local deprivation, ethnic origin and other factors contribute to health status, including the mechanisms through which this health differential comes about.

The methodologies used are quite different, for example Herwartz and Schley (2018) perform a stochastic frontier analysis on aggregate data from German localities to analyse how socio-economic factors influence the regional distribution of (in)efficiencies in the provision of healthcare services and find that efficiency is indeed linked with socio-economic variable such as education or share of immigrants. Gerdtham and Johannesson (2003) use individual health and employment data from Sweden to link unemployment status to increased risk of death.

Healthcare utilization patterns also reflect these disparities. Kangovi et al. (2013) showed that low SES patients favor hospital emergency services over primary care due to perceived barriers and a lack of trust in less familiar sequential care pathways. Such behavior further entrenches healthcare inequalities, as reliance on emergency services leads to poorer health outcomes, creating a vicious cycle among disadvantaged patients.

Analysing the case of Italy, Antonelli and Marini (2025) use regional-level aggregate data to find that socio-economic and institutional factors correlate strongly with a regional index of aggregate healthcare outcomes based on data such as mortality rate, life expectancy and share of people with chronic conditions. They also find that aggregate measures for income, education and institutional quality positively correlate with healthcare outcomes, together with measures of healthcare supply such as number of staff per inhabitant.

Also Franzini and Giannoni (2010) leverage on survey data from Italy and find that respondents living in regions with socioeconomic disadvantage, i.e. with higher poverty rates, elevated unemployment, or greater income inequality tend to report worse levels of self-rated health. These socioeconomic gradients are partly mediated by contextual factors, including deteriorated living conditions and a higher reliance on private out-of-pocket healthcare spending, which further reinforce disparities in health outcomes across regions.

Geographic considerations, such as neighborhood characteristics, are known to play a pivotal role in health outcomes. For instance, a systematic review by Pickett and Pearl (2001) outlines how neighborhood-level factors can significantly affect health behaviors and outcomes, leading to higher rates of morbidity and mortality in lower SES areas. Moreover, the differential impact of these socio-economic and geographic factors can be particularly

palpable in specific health conditions: Clegg et al. (2009) note that socioeconomic status can influence not only the likelihood of developing cancer but also the stage at which it is diagnosed, with disadvantaged populations presenting at later stages and facing poorer prognoses.

More specifically, this work speaks to the literature looking into how geographical factors significantly contribute to these disparities. Rural populations frequently encounter challenges in healthcare accessibility, leading to increased mortality rates from preventable conditions. To establish a connection between geographic characteristics and healthcare outcomes, extant literature uses a vast array of proxies to measure whether a locality or a patient should be classified as “rural.” Weinhold and Gurtner (2014) review the literature on the access to healthcare and healthcare shortages in rural or remote areas highlighting both a problem of insufficient and of inefficient (lower quality) provision.

Among the most relevant works, Knowles and Owen (2010) look at cross-country evidence on life expectancy and find it is correlated with the quality of formal and informal local institutions and also to geographical characteristics. More recently, Gibson et al. (2020) show that rural residents tend to have fewer healthcare options, indicating that their geographical isolation negatively affects their overall health. This rural-urban divide in healthcare access and outcome has been confirmed also for Hawaii (Bond-Smith et al., 2025) and China (Shen et al., 2025).

All in all, existing literature finds overwhelmingly evidence that regional-level factors such as local socio-economic status and geography profoundly impact hospital healthcare outcomes. Addressing these disparities has been object of various policy endeavours (OECD, 2004) and requires concerted efforts to redesign healthcare delivery models that are sensitive to the unique challenges faced by rural areas.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the institutional environment. In Section 3 we describe the data and the methodology. Section 4 describes the results of our empirical analysis. Section 5 concludes.

2. Institutional Background and Data

The Italian Healthcare System is a socialized system, free at the point of consumption for inpatient procedures and primary care services such as GP appointments. The central government retain legislative power and sets minimum standards of provision (“Essential Level of Care”, LEA), but regional governments have a large degree of autonomy on how to organize provision within their territory. Regions typically organize healthcare through Local Health Authorities (LHA, or ASL in Italian). Healthcare is funded by central government

transfers to Regions according to a capitation formula.

Different areas are served by a mix public hospital directly managed by local health authorities (LHAs), independent hospitals (e.g. university and research hospitals, mostly public) and private (both profit and non-profit) accredited hospitals, which are free at the point of consumption for patients. Finally, there are also fully private hospitals, in which patients pay for their care. Health insurance covers only a small fraction of out-of-pocket expenditures with employment-related insurance common only among the highest-earning individuals in the private sector.

The national agency for regional healthcare services (AGENAS) coordinates the “National [Clinical] Outcome Programme” (Programma Nazionale Esiti, PNE) . This programme is aimed at providing a number of clinical hospital-level performance measures for the sake of benchmarking, with a particular focus on promoting excellence and curbing inappropriateness. PNE includes data on numbers of specific procedures (e.g. the number of acute myocardial infarction in a given year/hospital), morbidity indices (e.g. 30-day or 1-year mortality) or process indices (e.g. number of patients re-admitted within 30 days, or number of surgeries performed within 2 days from hospitalization). All measures are risk-adjusted by AGENAS to account for the heterogeneity of case mix and are publicly available. All public and private-accredited hospitals are included and indices are calculated leveraging on hospital discharge records and vital statistics.

Out of the almost two hundred indices, we singled out a limited number that have been used in literature and that are more representative of different hospital outcomes:

1. Femur fracture: share of patients receiving surgery withing two days of hospitalization.
2. C-sections: share of primary C-sections.
3. Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI): 30-day mortality
4. Stroke: 1-year mortality

The first is an index of process efficiency for a routine hospital procedure, typically originating from a domestic accident like a fall. Other indices highlight the efficiency of both the hospital and the emergency care network (e.g. [2, 3]), other also point towards the capacity of hospitals to follow up patients after an acute episode and the link between territorial and hospital care (e.g. [4]). Finally, statistics on primary C-sections may also point towards demand-driven dynamics to do with patient’s preferences (possibly in itself linked with the efficiency of the healthcare sector in the locality).

We consider a hospital “catchment area” as municipalities within 50 km (crow’s flight) from the hospital location¹.

Our data also include a number of controls that encompass the characteristics of the population living within the catchment area. Our main interest is to understand how low-density and out-of-the-way areas are able to receive healthcare services. To define “rural” locations we rely on the national statistical institute (ISTAT) classification on the degree of urbanisation, which classify all municipalities as urban, semi-urban or rural.² About 60% of municipalities in Italy are classified as rural, but only 10% of the population lives there. We calculate the population-weighted values of a “rural” dummy within the catchment area of each hospital. This can be thought as measuring for any given hospital the share of (potential) users who reside in a rural area. From this measure we construct a dummy for all hospitals in the top quartile of the “rural” index.

From the Finance Ministry, we include the value of the average personal taxable income declared in the municipality (*income*, in year-2022 thousand euro per capita). We also include the hospital-level number of doctors employed in hospitals per thousand inhabitants.

Finally, we include demographic variables such as the municipal population, the share of people over 65 years old and the share of college graduates. All of these variables are common proxies for the demand for health services. As a further proxy for healthcare demand we include a measure of social capital, i.e. the municipality-level turnout at the most recent European Parliament election (2009 and 2014); this measure has been extensively used in the literature (see for example Amodio, 2012; Barone and Mocetti, 2016) as a proxy of pro-social behavior and voluntary contribution to public good. Social capital is also known to correlate with healthcare-seeking behavior (D’Hombres et al., 2008; Ciarrapico et al., 2023). As a proxy for healthcare supply we include the number of doctors per thousand inhabitants.³ All variables which are originally at the municipality level are calculated at the mean value at the hospital catchment area level, weighted by population.

As an example of the distribution of rural and non-rural municipalities and the distribution of hospitals, in Figure 1 we show the map of Italy with hospitals and their catchment areas and rural localities highlighted in green. To give some more details on the type of analysis we are performing, we chose also to show the map of one region (Tuscany): this region has both urban, semi-urban and rural locations (mountains to the East and sea-side to the West), and

¹We performed some robustness checks with distance measures between 30 and 70 km; results are stable across distances, with some loss of significance for lower values. Detailed regression results are available on request.

²The definition relies on population density at 1km square grid level and is codified by EUROSTAT. See [link](#).

³This measure is not available for some private accreditate hospital/years in our sample. Empirical results are qualitatively analogous also not including this regressor and are available upon request.

includes hospitals whose catchment areas are mostly rural or mostly urban. Our empirical analysis compare performance of hospitals according to the relative density of rural (potential) patients in their catchment areas.

Our empirical specification can be summarized as follows:

$$y_{ht} = \alpha + \beta \text{rural}_{ht} + \delta X_{ht} + r_r + \tau_t + \varepsilon_{ht} \quad (1)$$

where h indicate hospital-level variables, X is the battery of controls just specified, r and τ are local and year fixed effects. Finally, ε is the the usual white noise.

We include local fixed effects at the regional (NUTS-2) level, to account for unobserved heterogeneity and specific traits of each region’s healthcare system. For robustness, we also show regressions including macroarea (NUTS-1) fixed effects (in Appendix). Standard errors are clustered at the regional level.

Summary statistics are available in Table 1.

3. Empirical Analysis

Our data stretch from 2015 to 2023; in Figures 2-3 we provide a visual analysis of our data, showing the time trend of our dependent variables. There is a general improvement of healthcare outcomes over time: the share of femur fracture patients operated within 2 days increases (panel A of both Figures), the share of primary C-section decreases (panel B), AMI 30-day mortality decreases (panel C), while stroke 1-year mortality (panel D) shows a less straightforward trend. The second item one can notice is the sharp effect that the COVID pandemics (2020 and 2021) had on three out of the four outcomes, generating a strong drop in performance. The share of femur-fracture patients operated within two days dropped in 2020-2021 (panel A), the 1-year stroke mortality rate (panel D) has not yet recovered to pre-COVID levels, while the AMI 30-day survival rates (panel C) are still lower than their pre-COVID average at the end of our sample period. Quite surprisingly, outcomes are quite stable during COVID for primary C-section across the COVID years, continuing their slow decreasing pattern.

Looking at performance across sub-samples, Figure 2 depicts the average yearly level of each of the four outcomes separately for the North and the Center-South areas of the country⁴. For each of the four outcomes, healthcare quality appears substantially better in the North. Only the procedural index on femur fracture shows a “catching up” dynamic, with

⁴The North is composed by the eight northern regions: Piemonte, Valle d’Aosta, Lombardia, Trentino-Alto Adige, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Liguria and Emilia-Romagna. Sardinia is excluded from our analysis for the peculiar characteristics of its geography and healthcare offer.

very similar outcomes between North and Center-South in the last year in our data (2023).

In Figure 3 we show instead the average level of each of our four indices separating according to whether the average income level in their catchment area is above or below the median. Poor and rich areas have similar evolution over time, but poorer areas appear to have substantially worse outcomes for all the four indices. In poor areas the share of femur fracture patients operated within two days is small, primary C-section are more frequent and mortality for both AMI (30-day) and stroke (1-year) are higher. There is no visual evidence of any catching up if not for the femur-fracture index.

To look into whether rural and non rural areas differ, we now turn our attention to the regression analysis in Table 2. We regress in each column a different healthcare outcome according to the specification described in Equation 1. In column (1) we look at the share of patients operated for femur fracture within two days of hospitalization, in column (2) at the share of primary C-sections, in column (3) at the 30-day mortality rate for acute myocardial infarction (AMI), in column (4) at the 1-year mortality rate for stroke. Our results show that rural areas receive worse hospital treatment for three out of the four indices analyzed: the share of femur fracture patients operated within two days is 3.2 percentage points lower, C-sections are 2.2 percentage points higher and AMI 30-day mortality is 0.6 higher. There is no statistically significant effect on 1-year stroke mortality. This points towards a widespread evidence of worse healthcare provision on a number of dimensions: procedural efficiency on a routine procedure (as from femur fracture) is lower, inappropriateness is higher (as from C-section) and mortality for a condition that is heavily time-dependent (and therefore dependent on both the hospital and the emergency network readiness). This same dynamic is visible in smaller hospital (lowest quartile in terms of number of procedures), where the femur fracture index is 5.6pp lower, C-sections are 2.6pp higher and AMI mortality is 0.8pp higher. We can also see how private hospital are more ready when it comes to executing procedure (13pp higher rate for femur fracture, 12pp higher rate for C-section) but also more effective with AMI (0.6pp lower mortality). Other control variable have less consistent interpretation, but we also need to remember that our regression includes region and year fixed effect, absorbing a fair amount of within-region and within-year variability. On the supply side, our regressions highlight that the amount of doctors per thousand inhabitants is significantly linked with lower C-section rate and lower AMI mortality rate. One may also notice that income is positively correlated to efficiency in the femur fracture index, but also positively correlated with C-section rate. This latter result may point towards the fact that part of the inappropriateness for C-section may be due to cultural factors also on the demand side. These results are robust in terms of sign and significance also if we include macroarea (instead of regional) fixed effects (see Table A1 in the Appendix).

To dig further in the outcomes, we perform an heterogeneity analysis on our main results, splitting our sample first between North and Center-South and then between poor and rich areas, according to the median value of the personal income. From Figures 2-3 we know that there are important baseline differences between different areas of the country and between different income levels across time, but it is of our interest to investigate whether this affects differently rural and non-rural areas. We use our baseline specification as in Equation 1 splitting our sample as described. In Figure 4 we show graphically the coefficient of the *rural* dummy of each regression, while regression results (only showing the coefficient of the *rural* dummy) are available in Table 3; we also include the average value of the dependent variable in the split sample, to ease the interpretation of the marginal effects.

Hospital performance on femur-fracture surgeries (panel A of Figure 4) is not statistically different between North and Centre-South, even if performance is on average better in the North by about 8 percentage points. When it comes to income, we can see that in rich areas rural hospital performance is about 7.6 percentage points worse than urban ones, thus closing the gap between rich and poor areas.

For C-sections, in Table 3 we can note a stark difference in the average values of the dependent variable, with substantially higher rates in the Centre-South and in richer areas. Heterogeneity analysis (also shown in panel B of Figure 4) does not highlight any statistical difference between rural and non-rural areas across sub-samples.

We can also see from our results on AMI mortality (Table 3 and panel C of Figure 4), that rural locations have worse outcomes than urban ones both in the North and in richer areas and that average performance of southern (poorer) hospitals is about one percentage point lower than northern (richer) ones.

Finally, we look into the 1-year mortality rate for stroke. Our main analysis found no difference between rural and non-rural areas, but the heterogeneity analysis shows a different picture. The territorial and income difference in mean values is striking, with mortality rates 3.9pp higher in Centre-South and 3.5pp higher in poorer areas. We can see that in the Center-South and in poor areas, rural hospital perform even worse than urban ones, further widening the divide. This in itself would be worth further exploration, as 1-year mortality rates are the product of an array of factors, including hospital efficiency, primary healthcare provision for acute patients and socio-economic factors related to the patient, their family and community.

Our results seem to point to the fact that rural locations compound with other factors (such as being in a territorial or economically disadvantaged area) and determine substantially worse longer-term healthcare outcomes.

4. Conclusions

In this paper we investigated how hospital performance of Italian hospitals differs between rural and non-rural areas, using detailed hospital-level outcomes combined with rich socio-economic and geographic information at the catchment-area level. By focusing on four different clinically and policy-relevant indicators, we provide a comprehensive picture of how territorial characteristics shape healthcare quality beyond standard demand and supply factors.

Our results point to a clear and robust pattern: hospitals serving a larger share of rural populations perform worse on several key dimensions of care. Procedural efficiency, measured by the share of femur fracture patients operated on within two days, is significantly lower in rural settings. Indicators capturing inappropriateness and emergency care performance—such as primary Caesarean section rates and 30-day mortality following acute myocardial infarction—also reveal sizeable rural penalties. These findings persist after controlling for income, demographic structure, healthcare staffing, social capital, and unobserved regional heterogeneity, suggesting that rural disadvantage is not merely a proxy for lower socio-economic status or weaker healthcare supply.

The heterogeneity analysis also sheds light on the interaction between rural status and broader spatial inequalities. While baseline healthcare performance is generally better in the North and in richer areas, rural hospitals in these contexts often underperform relative to their urban counterparts, narrowing—but in a perverse way—the gap with poorer or southern areas. For stroke 1-year mortality the urban-rural divide instead widens the divide, hitting only already disadvantaged territories (Center-South and lower-income areas). This suggests that rurality represents a distinct dimension of disadvantage that operates even within otherwise well-performing healthcare systems.

From a policy perspective, our findings carry several implications. First, strategies aimed at improving healthcare equity cannot rely solely on regional redistribution or increases in average funding levels. Even within regions, rural areas face structural challenges related to distance, scale, and workforce availability that directly affect hospital performance. Second, investments in emergency networks, transport infrastructure, and coordination between hospitals and territorial services appear particularly crucial for time-sensitive conditions. Third, policies targeting workforce allocation—such as incentives for healthcare professionals to work in rural hospitals—may help mitigate some of the observed gaps.

More broadly, the results support a move towards explicitly place-based healthcare policies that recognize the specific constraints faced by rural and low-density areas. As demographic aging and depopulation trends are likely to intensify in many parts of Europe, addressing

rural healthcare disparities will become increasingly central to the sustainability and equity of national health systems.

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FIGURE 1. Rural municipalities (in green), hospitals and catchment areas (year 2022, hospitals with AMI data).

(A) Tuscany region

(B) Italy

FIGURE 2. Healthcare outcomes by macroarea

(A) Femur fracture: share of surgery within 2 days

(B) Share of primary C-Sections

(C) AMI: 30-day mortality

(D) Stroke: 1-year mortality

FIGURE 3. Healthcare outcomes: poor vs rich areas

(A) Femur fracture: share of surgery within 2 days

(B) Share of primary C-Sections

(C) AMI: 30-day mortality

(D) Stroke: 1-year mortality

FIGURE 4. Heterogeneity Analysis

(A) Hip fracture

(B) Share of primary C-Sections

(C) AMI 30-day mortality

(D) Stroke 1-year mortality

TABLE 1. Summary statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	N
Femur fracture: % surgery within 2 days	64.204	20.626	0.98	100	3778
% of primary C-sections	24.765	11.72	0.26	95.52	3156
AMI: 30-day mortality	16.285	5.921	1.95	57.56	2073
Stroke: 1-year mortality	8.434	4.189	0.63	100	3164
Small hospital	0.235	0.424	0	1	3778
Independent hospital	0.119	0.324	0	1	3778
Private-accredited hospitals	0.084	0.277	0	1	3778
University/Research Hospital	0.035	0.184	0	1	3778
Population	1943.563	1746.9	114.445	6416.974	3566
% graduates	0.168	0.048	0.062	0.294	3592
% elderly	23.212	2.25	17.852	29.866	3566
Income, pp	21.234	3.942	11.023	36.408	3566
Social Capital	0.59	0.12	0.343	0.847	3461

TABLE 2. Main results

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Femur	C-Sec	AMI-30d	Stroke-1y
Rural	-3.185** (1.243)	2.169*** (0.521)	0.555** (0.219)	0.558 (0.365)
Small hospital	-5.557*** (0.979)	2.619*** (0.447)	0.796*** (0.236)	0.609 (0.409)
Self-gov hospital	0.604 (1.114)	-0.819 (0.572)	-0.561*** (0.211)	0.388 (0.383)
Private hospital	13.584*** (1.777)	12.229*** (0.979)	-0.761** (0.386)	-1.161 (0.864)
Uni/Research hospital	8.333*** (1.937)	2.315** (1.170)	0.033 (0.453)	-1.246* (0.680)
Doctors per k inhab.	0.031** (0.014)	-0.015** (0.007)	-0.011*** (0.004)	0.009 (0.010)
Population ('000)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.001** (0.000)	-0.000** (0.000)	0.001** (0.000)
% graduates	-0.532*** (0.167)	-0.318*** (0.086)	0.010 (0.031)	0.002 (0.067)
% elderly	0.370 (0.407)	1.679*** (0.202)	-0.338*** (0.104)	-0.401*** (0.150)
Income	1.492*** (0.317)	0.552*** (0.149)	-0.080 (0.064)	-0.386*** (0.135)
Social capital	-8.806** (4.295)	-7.027*** (2.094)	1.166 (1.039)	-0.783 (2.424)
Constant	31.376*** (11.355)	-13.805*** (5.145)	17.607*** (3.002)	32.544*** (4.053)
R ²	0.303	0.530	0.125	0.289
N	2560	2155	2013	1628

Standard errors in parentheses

All regressions include region and year fixed effects.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

TABLE 3. Heterogeneity Analysis

Femur fracture				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	North	South	Poor	Rich
Rural	-2.549*	-3	-1.329	-7.680***
	(1.483)	(2.011)	(1.971)	(1.515)
R ²	0.223	0.304	0.325	0.285
N	952	1608	1473	1087
Mean dep. var.	68.377	60.801	60.813	68.862

C-section				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	North	South	Poor	Rich
Rural	1.514**	1.326	2.149**	1.160*
	(0.620)	(0.843)	(0.845)	(0.659)
R ²	0.329	0.450	0.523	0.490
N	700	1455	1236	919
Mean dep. var.	17.943	29.618	29.090	20.195

AMI 30-day mortality				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	North	South	Poor	Rich
Rural	0.762***	0.556	-0.121	0.664**
	(0.261)	(0.364)	(0.370)	(0.271)
R ²	0.151	0.139	0.106	0.160
N	832	1191	1302	1000
Mean dep. var.	7.978	8.786	9.023	7.882

Stroke 1-year mortality				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	North	South	Poor	Rich
Rural	-0.081	1.174**	1.168**	-0.655
	(0.471)	(0.589)	(0.588)	(0.554)
R ²	0.204	0.244	0.281	0.224
N	661	967	945	683
Mean dep. var.	14.345	18.213	18.056	14.512

Standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

All regressions include region and year fixed effects and the full battery of controls.

Appendix

TABLE A1. Robustness check: Macroarea fixed effects

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Femur	C-Sec	AMI-30d	Stroke-1y
Rural	-10.249*** (0.982)	2.344*** (0.466)	-0.391* (0.206)	0.879*** (0.328)
Small hospital	-4.032*** (1.012)	2.811*** (0.486)	-0.189 (0.228)	0.627 (0.416)
Self-gov hospital	0.754 (1.077)	-1.616*** (0.531)	-1.573*** (0.223)	0.867** (0.342)
Private hospital	9.616*** (1.307)	12.005*** (0.953)	-0.938*** (0.258)	0.025 (0.693)
Uni/Research hospital	8.487*** (1.896)	0.486 (1.159)	-2.524*** (0.352)	-0.959 (0.632)
Doctors per k inhab.	0.036** (0.015)	-0.007 (0.005)	0.004 (0.005)	0.008 (0.010)
Population ('000)	-0.003*** (0.000)	0.002*** (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	0.001*** (0.000)
% graduates	-1.256*** (0.151)	0.092 (0.082)	-0.053 (0.033)	-0.111* (0.057)
% elderly	-0.099 (0.269)	0.464*** (0.134)	0.066 (0.054)	0.019 (0.085)
Income	2.789*** (0.298)	-0.237* (0.143)	0.088 (0.059)	-0.239** (0.120)
Social capital	-12.965*** (3.815)	-9.538*** (1.885)	0.684 (0.776)	-5.722*** (1.873)
Constant	38.258*** (8.020)	21.978*** (3.457)	13.210*** (1.534)	23.684*** (2.665)
R ²	0.209	0.469	0.085	0.247
N	2560.000	2155.000	2625.000	1628.000

Standard errors in parentheses

All regressions include macroarea and year fixed effects.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$